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THE SOCIAL INTERFACES DEVELOPMENT FOR CULTURAL CREATIVITY INDUSTRY: A USER-CENTRED DESIGN CASE STUDY ON CHINESE SHADOW PUPPETRY

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ABSTRACT

The Digital Shadow Play is an interactive multimedia interface design, expected to be the new form of artistic expression of the traditional leather puppet. Because of the complex cultural context of the heritage, there had been few design case studies of the social interfaces of the digital shadow play for cultural heritage exhibitions. This study aims to design and validate prototypes of social interface of the digital shadow play based on a design case study exhibited in museums, which, in turn to define the design principle for future study.

Keywords: social interfaces, socialability, digital shadow play

INTRODUCTION

The public and social context of museums and their increase in civic popularity demands new interaction designs for multiple users that depart from interactive kiosks that were once a mainstay of museums. Social interaction in digitally augmented spaces take different forms, from on-site or remote communication to collaborative learning, gaming and playing. Social interfaces thereby support people working, learning, playing, and discussing together, focusing on the same content while physically co-located and co-present. This term encourages a focus on the kinds of activity to be supported rather than on the design of an interface or on a particular type of system.

The earlier study examined the complex visual content of the Digital Shadow Theater interface (Chen *et al.*, 2010). In this study, it aims to design and validate prototypes of social interface of the digital shadow play based on a design case study exhibited in a museum, which, in turn to define the design principle for future study. This paper will answer the basic research questions of the design principle and to define the socialability of the interface. It hopes that this study could stimulate digital creativity through understanding the culture context of the heritage.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the shadow play, the shadow of fur made characters with delicate carving and brilliant colours shadows. These shadow characters, which are projected by the man-made lights behind the curtain, could be seen by the audience in front of the curtain. The Piyong artists behind the curtain control the actions of the characters using sticks fastened to the shadow characters (see Figure 1). Since the control of characters can also be done by people without professional training, the shadow play and associated culture, carving and performing and storytelling techniques have been well preserved by the Ministry of Education. Thus, shadow play and shadow paper crafting are compulsory courses taught in junior high

school, learning handed down from generation to generation by teachers.

Since many exhibitions are not designed as convivial experiences, many people have all experienced not being able to take part during group interaction. In order to enable all to see and interact, it requires handing the device around, sequencing the interaction and providing a narrative model for those not in the loop at a given stage. This creates a new user experience than when a whole group can view the same content, such as photos on a large TV screen. Social interfaces thereby support people working, learning, playing, and discussing together (Jaimes *et al.*, 2006; Hornecker *et al.*, 2007).

Figure 1. Shadow Play in Taiwan

Because of the complex cultural context of the heritage, there had been few design case studies of the social interfaces for cultural heritage exhibitions. There is also a need for design principle, design guideline, frameworks and literature surveys that draw together empirical and observational findings on how groups of collocated visitors interact and work with the medium (Nielsen *et al.*, 2009; Snibbe, *et al.*, 2009).

METHOD

Based on the culture context of the shadow play, this research conducted a series of design case study using multi-touch technology, which aims to display and allow users to control two-dimensional (2D)

virtual characters on the screen using their fingers. Various versions of 2D characters are designed based on the famous story “Wu-Song and the Tiger”.

In prior of this study, a prototype was developed and exhibited at the “Exhibition of Shadow Art and Culture” at the National Museum of History in Taiwan, from 23rd April to 17th Oct. 2010, which the findings were published in CREATE 2010 (Chen *et al.*, 2010).

In this study, the prototype was improved based on the problems identified by this earlier case study. It is developed based on the 22”, projected, capacitive technology (PCT), which has multi-user capabilities of fifty touch-points. It was exhibited at the special exhibition “FTP://Future.Tradition.Puppet”, organized and exhibited at the Kaohsiung Museum of History, from June 19th to 26th September, 2010 (see Figure 2). The observations were employed using a digital video recorder to address the research questions in a qualitative manner. A total of 360mins of video data was successfully captured in this study. Two observers were invited to record the activities of the target population with the interface on the same days.

Figure 2. The digital shadow show “Wu-Song and Tiger”, as demonstrated at the Exhibition “FTP://Future.Tradition.Puppet”, organized and exhibited at the Kaohsiung Museum of History.

Owing to concerns about participants affecting the community-based study, this study did not allow the experimenter and observers to interact with the audiences. Thus, this study aimed to increase its

validity by inviting two well-trained observers to the exhibitions who helps to record the visitors' activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the observation analysis, the video data was interpreted into notices, which were clustered into issues according to research questions. The feedback from the exhibition organizers, visitors and tourist guides were collected to support the video data.

A total of 360+mins of video data was successfully captured. Data from the field observations uncovered issues that had mainly to do with the cognition of the visual feedback with a multi-touch screen.

DISCUSSION

In this case study, all touch events are captured by PCT display. It is cost-effective, however, the following failures were found, including the display's inaccuracy, the inability to use multiple fingers to control the characters naturally, the touch event size is too small to use the fingertip to operate, etc. One problem detected was that if the user hit the characters that were not fully controlled by the touch event, then users had to stop playing in order to readjust the components. Indeed it de-motivated the users to interact with the interface. A similar problem was also found with the second design case.

Data from the field observations are clustered in four issues to form a design principle:

- **Screen size:** It is found that users preferred the large screen interaction because they had more freedom during interaction and could solve the presented task significantly faster.
- **Touch size:** It can be said that the larger the size to trigger a touch, the higher the accuracy of the interaction. However, touch is a very intuitive modality for interacting with objects displayed on surfaces.
- **User-friendly:** It is highly risky for an audience, in particular of children, to damage the stage and themselves. For instance, the physics engine is integrated for both design cases, which allows the creation to "jump", "hit" and "fall". However, the introduction of this new element highlighted some problems with the interpretation of the shadow characters' movements which could not easily be understood by children. Thus, when the shadow characters sometimes cause a temporary disappearance, users might damage the stage due to their over-vigorous activities.
- **Sharability:** In this study, it is explored that the number of the visual characters on the screen could limit the number of the players. Based on the result analysis, when the stage having two visual characters on the screen, the number of the player allowed to play on the screen were ranged from 1 to 4 people.

Thus, the socialability of the digital shadow play could be defined as "Natural capability of the multi-touch user interface that allows users to share user experience, subjects to the transaction spaces, visibility, audibility, and the ability to enter and physically occupy a space". As for the research methodology for the evaluation of the multi-touch interaction, there is an insufficient, objective, evaluation metric, which needs to be further studied.

Further findings were: firstly, based on feedback from the exhibition organizers, visitors and tourist guides, the exhibition met the goal which is to foster enjoyment, engagement, empathy, self-reflection and learning through the use of social interfaces. Secondly, the study found that the "no dialogue" situation is the symbolic of the medium. Such type of the social interfaces is deemed as a new narrative form: the absence of words allows the user to see the true meaning of the story.

CONCLUSION

Owing to the impact of the modern media, the shadow theatres have been disappearing in contemporary society. Nowadays, there are only five shadow show troupes in Taiwan and these are considered to be a priceless cultural asset.

This study has stimulated creativity through understanding the culture context of the shadow play. The findings can provide the design principle that is devoted to the creation of intuitive, user-friendly interfaces. As for the research method for the evaluation of the interaction and usability of the models, the lack of a sufficient, objective, evaluation metric seems to offer fruitful opportunities for further study.

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